

**БИОГРАФИЯ ЦЗЭН ГОФАНЯ: ДЕТСТВО, ЮНОСТЬ И НАЧАЛО
КАРЬЕРЫ (1811-1872)****THE BIOGRAPHY OF ZENG GUOFAN: CHILDHOOD, YOUTH, AND
EARLY CAREER (1811-1872)****КОНСТАНТИНОВА ЕКАТЕРИНА АЛЕКСАНДРОВНА,***кандидат философских наук, преподаватель,
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Предметом исследования является биография Цзэн Г из Ань. Рассмотрены детство, юность, ранние годы Цзэн Гофаня, его семья и образование. Проанализирована предыстория того, как Цзэн Гофань стал великим полководцем, военачальником на своем жизненном пути. Обоснована идея о том, что его письменное наследие включает в себя не только приказы, военные записки, но и письма, стихи, донесения. Сделан вывод, что анализ биографии Цзэн Гофаня позволяет нам сделать вывод, что, несмотря на различные сложные ситуации, благодаря его силе воли, упорству, дисциплине и целеустремленности, он и по сей день остается классической фигурой для своей страны.

The subject of the study is the biography of Tseng G from An. The author examines Zeng Guofan's childhood, youth, early years, his family and education. The background of how Zeng Guofan became a great commander, a military leader on his life path is analyzed. The idea is substantiated that his written legacy includes not only orders, military notes, but also letters, poems, reports. It is concluded that an analysis of Zeng Guofan's biography allows us to conclude that, despite various difficult situations, thanks to his willpower, perseverance, discipline and determination, he remains a classic figure for his country to this day.

Ключевые слова: Цзэн Гофань, биография, “самоусиление”, конфуцианство, китайская история, тайпины.

Key words: Zeng Guofan, biography, “self-strengthening”, Confucianism, Chinese history, taipins.

Zeng Guofan (1811-1872) stands as one of the most prominent and significant figures in the history of mid 19th century China. Within Russian-language research literature, he is primarily renowned as the "executioner of the Taiping Rebellion" [1, p. 675]. Indeed, Zeng Guofan made a brilliant career through his efforts in combating the Taiping rebels (1850-1864). However, his public and political career did not culminate there. He emerged as the ideological inspiration and architect of the "self-strengthening" policy (1860-1895), aimed at assimilating Western advancements and innovations while preserving cultural traditions. As part of the implementation of the "self-strengthening" policy, Zeng Guofan, along with his associates (Li Hongzhang (1823–1901), Zhang Zhidong (1837–1909), Zuo Zongtang (1812-1885)), organized the procurement of European warships and weapons. Moreover, based on his own educational and training programs, he established the largest Hunan Army, which surpassed the imperial forces in both strength and discipline.

Furthermore, the renowned strategist held the highest academic degree of Jinshi and was a member of the Hanlin Academy. He is the author of numerous literary, philosophical, and pedagogical works [2]. Additionally, as a representative of the Tunchen literary school, Zeng Guofan is recognized as an innovator in the development of refined literature concepts [3]. The 19th century holds a special place in the political history and the history of social and philosophical thought in China, representing a period of radical changes in imperial society and the re-evaluation of many fundamental spiritual values and orientations of national culture. These processes were triggered, on one hand, by an irreversible internal crisis that engulfed the key spheres of life of the last Chinese empire – the Qing Dynasty (1644-1911), and on the other hand, by the growing political, economic, and cultural expansion of Western powers led by the British Empire, France, Japan, and Germany. At that time, the representatives of China's political and intellectual elite recognized unprecedented challenges: the country's true geopolitical position, the need to preserve national authenticity while integrating the technological and humanitarian advancements of Western civilization to modernize the social structure, manufacturing base, and armed forces.

One of the most prominent statesmen, public figures, and thinkers of China during this period was Zeng Guofan (1811-1872), who made significant practical and theoretical contributions to the "self-strengthening" policy (1860-1895). The development of this policy laid the foundation for Chinese socio-political thought in the 20th century. It is still partially utilized by the leadership circles and ideologists of the People's Republic of China. Therefore, the study of Zeng Guofan's life path, worldview, and theoretical legacy is an urgently necessary condition for understanding both the "self-strengthening" policy and the overall historical and political situation that emerged in China in the second half of the 19th century.

The renewed attention to Zeng Guofan's ideas in the contemporary development of Russian society is driven not only by an interest in monuments of a different sociocultural environment but also by a desire to consider the accumulated historical philosophical experience for comprehending the social realities of nowadays.

In the research literature, there is no consensus on the main periods of Zeng Guofan's life and creative path. Authors often retell his biography without highlighting specific stages. For example, in the work of Chinese scholar Dong Caishi, which the author relies upon, Zeng Guofan's biography is presented in detail by dates, but there is no delineation into distinct periods and generalizations [4].

The delineation of stages in Zeng Guofan's life journey is undoubtedly necessary. Primarily, it allows tracing the correlation between the main periods of his life and his creative output. Additionally, it provides an opportunity to determine the extent to which specific periods of his bureaucratic, political, military, and literary activities influenced his worldview. Furthermore, an accurate reconstruction and understanding of Zeng Guofan's views are impossible without considering his personal life realities (changes in social status, personal experiences, etc.).

If we take radical changes in his status as the base for structuring biographical material, the following periodization can be proposed:

1811-1833 the period of upbringing. Childhood, adolescence, youth.

1833-1850 the period of civil service.

1850s-1860s the period of military success, associated with the suppression of the Taiping Rebellion (1850-1864), military career.

1860-1872 the period of formation and implementation of the "self-strengthening" policy (1860-1895).

This article focuses solely on the first two periods from 1811 to 1850. Undoubtedly, Zeng Guofan's personal experiences, his military and bureaucratic activities significantly influenced the formation of his worldview, reflected in certain perspectives that evolved with changes in his status. This periodization also considers the possibility of the main milestones in his career overlapping

with stages of his creative development. However, the proposed periodization is not definitive and does not represent the only possible option. The primary emphasis is placed on his career success and achievements. It is necessary to note that the periodization is made considering Zeng Guofan's career advancement in both civil and military spheres, yet it does not reflect the transformation of his literary and philosophical views.

Zeng Guofan was born on November 26, 1811, in the Hunan province, Xiangshan county [5, p. 371]. His second name was Bohan, and his literary pseudonym was Dishen. It is crucial to provide the historical context of Zeng Guofan's socio-political actions for understanding the specificity of his life path.

Zeng Guofan was destined to be born during one of the challenging periods of the Qing dynasty's rule (1644-1911). This was an eventful period - China, from being a weak, closed country, gradually transformed into a member of the global community. However, it was a time-consuming process preceded by violent intervention of China by Western powers, its division into spheres of influence among powerful states, unequal treaties signed following the Opium Wars, a series of endless rebellions within the country (the Taiping Rebellion (1850-1864), the Nian Rebellion (1853-1868)), the formation of the doctrine of the "movement for the adoption of Western practices" of the "self-strengthening movement" (1860-1895). Zeng Guofan was somehow involved in most of these events.

Practically nothing is known about his parents, except for mentions that his father was a scholar. Additionally, Zeng Guofan had brothers - Zeng Goyan (1820), Zeng Gohua (1822), Zeng Gojuan (1824), and Zeng Gobao (1828).

Zeng Guofan, still a young man, arrived in Changsha to participate in the examinations and completed his education at the Lianbin School. It was here where he spent his youth. Raised alongside his brothers in Confucian traditions, he received a corresponding education. In 1833, at the age of twenty-two, Zeng Guofan married a young woman named Ouyan Di [5, p. 372]. Growing up in a traditional Chinese family, Zeng Guofan was accustomed to the principles of "filial piety", "humaneness", and cared for and assisted his younger siblings.

Those few facts about his youth lead to an assumption that Zeng Guofan received a traditional upbringing, thus his views were shaped under the influence of Confucian teachings. Moreover, individuals of this type were characterized by unconditioned loyalty to the ruling dynasty. It can also be assumed that the popular unrest happening throughout his youth had some influence on shaping Zeng Guofan's worldview and his interest in the state's affairs.

The second stage of Zeng Guofan's life path falls between 1833 and 1850. It is during this period that his career path begins: he attains the degree of Xiucan, then in 1834, the degree of Juren. Several years later, in 1838, still quite young, he attains the degree of Jinshi [5, p. 372]. Furthermore, he becomes one of the top performers among those who passed the examination for the position of Jinshi – Shijishi.

Therefore, he was retained for service at the Hanlin Academy. This method of replenishing the Academy was practiced quite often. As biographers write, during this period, he became engrossed in the study of Neo-Confucianism, delving into the teachings of Zhu Xi (1130-1200).

During this period, the issue of opium importation and trade became increasingly critical for China. Since the mid 1830s, officials from various provinces sent reports to the Chinese capital with advice and proposals regarding the prohibition of opium importation. It was precisely this substance that served as the cause for the outbreak of the First Opium War (1840-1842), when in April 1840, the British government declared war on China. As a result, the unfair Treaty of Nanjing was signed, compelling China to fulfil a series of harsh conditions.

In response to this, Zeng Guofan noted in his diary: "Great achievements are made through small steps. We should rejoice in the natural course of events" [6, p. 15]. In 1843, while still serving in the Hanlin Academy, Zeng Guofan undertook his first examinations in the province of Sichuan

[5]. Zeng Guofan's diligence, perseverance, and talent resulted in new promotions: he initially served as the second assistant minister of the Ministry of Rites (Libu) (it oversaw state ceremonies and examinations) in 1849, and later as the second assistant minister in the Ministry of War (Bingbu). Zeng Guofan made a remarkable scholarly career, starting as Xiucai to a member of the Hanlin Academy. Drawing parallels with academic degrees in modern Russia, it can be said that in such a short time he ascended from a master's to a doctorate degree. It is noteworthy that he obtained the main scholarly degrees (Xiucai, Juren, Jinshi) within five years. The efficiency of Confucian teachings found undeniable confirmation in his rapid career advancement. Why was such rapid career advancement possible? Perhaps, Zeng Guofan had a certain patron guiding him. However, this thesis remains speculative as such information is absent in primary sources. The only plausible explanation is that success across various fields within such a short timeframe is attainable only by an individual that possesses unwavering determination, resilience, intellectual acumen, adept self-organization, and relentless pursuit of set objectives.

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